

1 **Activation of NFKBID by HPV16 E7.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 E7 molecular functions, binding partners and network interactants remain incompletely defined. We
7 studied E7 molecular function through measurement of total transcription by RNA-sequencing in HPV-
8 C33A cells following ectopic expression of HPV16 E7. We demonstrate here activation of *Nfkbid* by
9 HPV16 HPV E7.

10 Citations

11 1. McLaughlin-Drubin, M.E. and Münger, K., 2009. The human papillomavirus E7 oncoprotein.
12 *Virology*, 384(2), pp.335-344.

13 2. Arnold, C.N., Pirie, E., Dosenovic, P., McInerney, G.M., Xia, Y., Wang, N., Li, X., Siggs, O.M.,
14 Karlsson Hedestam, G.B. and Beutler, B., 2012. A forward genetic screen reveals roles for *Nfkbid*, *Zeb1*,
15 and *Ruvbl2* in humoral immunity. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109(31),
16 pp.12286-12293.

17 3. Dwyer, J.R., Racine, J.J., Chapman, H.D., Quinlan, A., Presa, M., Stafford, G.A., Schmitz, I. and
18 Serreze, D.V., 2022. *Nfkbid* overexpression in nonobese diabetic mice elicits complete type 1 diabetes
19 resistance in part associated with enhanced thymic deletion of pathogenic CD8 T cells and increased
20 numbers and activity of regulatory T cells. *The Journal of Immunology*, 209(2), pp.227-237.

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